

“ASSESSMENT” METHOD IN TEACHING IN ACCORDANCE WITH SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT CONCEPTS AND THE TOPIC OF OXIDES

Qudratov Javohir Jahongir o'g'li

Chirchik State Pedagogical University

Faculty of Physics and Chemistry

3rd year student of Chemistry Education

<https://orcid.org/0009-0000-0623-2433>

qudratovjahongirovichjavohir@gmail.com

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Abstract: our article below presents efforts to make chemistry interesting and achieve sustainable development. In order to further increase students' interest in chemistry, to study the topic in depth and to apply it to life, sustainable development education is included. The "Assessment" method was used to assess how well this topic was studied.

Key words: sustainable development, chemistry, assessment, oxides, naming, extraction, acidic oxides, basic oxides, amphoteric oxides, neutral oxides

Introduction

Large-scale reforms are being implemented in the education system of our country to introduce advanced foreign educational technologies and information and communication tools into the educational process, increase the intensity and efficiency of training, and adapt it to world standards. The Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. RF-60 dated January 28, 2022 “On the Development Strategy of New Uzbekistan for 2022-2026” establishes significant work to radically improve the quality of education and raise the knowledge and skills of teaching staff to international standards in order to build a Renaissance Renaissance in New Uzbekistan and its surroundings. is being implemented, as well as the prospects for national development are being explored. Today, the role of innovation and information and communication technologies in achieving sustainable development is becoming increasingly important. The article below focuses on sustainable development and a deeper study of chemistry.

Literature Review And Methods

Inorganic substances are divided into simple and complex substances according to their composition. Compounds, in turn, are divided into oxides, bases, acids and salts.

Oxides are a class of inorganic compounds widely distributed in nature. Oxides include such well-known compounds as water H_2O , sand SiO_2 , clay CaO ,

Al_2O_3 , carbon dioxide CO_2 , and magnetite Fe_3O_4 . Oxides are in liquid, solid and gaseous states.

Oxides are widely used in the food industry, medicine, construction and chemical industries. The general formula of oxides: E_xO_y . E - atoms of a chemical element; O - oxygen atoms; x, y - indices indicating the number of atoms of elements forming the oxide.

According to their chemical properties, oxides are divided into salt-forming and non-salt-forming. Non-salt-forming oxides do not interact with acids or alkalis. There are few non-salt-forming oxides:

N_2O , NO, CO, SiO.

Salt-forming oxides are oxides that react with acids or bases to form salts and water. Salt-forming oxides include basic, acidic, and amphoteric oxides. The only element that does not form oxides is fluorine, which combines with oxygen to form oxygen fluoride OF_2 . This is because fluorine is a more reactive element than oxygen.

Oxides are divided into several groups depending on their reaction with water, bases and acids:

Basic oxides: Na_2O , BaO, CuO, etc.

Acidic oxides: CO_2 , SO_3 , P_2O_5 , etc.

Amphoteric oxides: ZnO, Al_2O_3 , Sb_2O_3 , etc.

Non-salt-forming: CO, NO, N_2O , etc.

Additionally, the concepts of sustainable development education to the explanation of the topic of oxides will not only become a modern method of education, but will also increase the interest and relevance of science for the student. CaO is found in limestone and marble. This oxide is a major component

of the construction industry. Calcium oxide is the main raw material in cement production, which forms calcium silicates and other compounds during the cement production process. It is also useful in pest control, as it changes the pH and decomposes some organic substances.

CO₂ is a carbon dioxide gas, which is the main component of the gases emitted by cars today, gases emitted by oil burned to produce electricity, gases produced by forest fires, natural gas burned for our daily needs, and gases emitted by wood. Carbon dioxide, which is released in large quantities, reacts with rain and snow water and turns into carbonic acid.

The carbonic acid formed reacts with the CaCO₃ and MgCO₃ compounds in rocks and soil to form bicarbonate salts. In this process, the insoluble salts are converted into carbonate salts and the water-soluble salts are converted into water-soluble bicarbonate salts.

This process is also observed in groundwater. That is, as a result of the decomposition of many organic compounds in the ground, carbon dioxide is formed between the subsurface layers, and bicarbonates above, as a result, combine with water to form carbonic acid. In this case, groundwater also reacts with CaCO₃ and MgCO₃ compounds in the subsurface layers with H₂CO₃ dissolved in water to form soluble Ca(HCO₃)₂ and Mg(HCO₃)₂. This gives temporary hardness. When teaching these processes to students, we can give an example of the negative consequences of releasing large amounts of carbon dioxide into the atmosphere.

SiO₂ silicon (IV) oxide, sand. Used in construction for plastering walls. CaO+H₂O+SiO₂=CaSiO₃ calcium silicate acts as a glue, so our plastered wall becomes as hard as concrete. It is also one of the main components in the production of cement and concrete. It helps increase the strength of concrete and improve its quality. Silicon (IV) oxide plays an important role in the production of glass. It is the main component of the glass material, providing its hardness and transparency. Silicon dioxide is used in some cosmetics, including powders and toothpastes. It is also used in pharmaceuticals, to help formulate or preserve some drugs. Silicon dioxide is used as an adsorbent, for example, in water and air purification or in the separation of chemicals.

N₂O laughing gas. Nitrous oxide is widely used as a pain reliever and anesthetic. It is used in medical procedures and dental treatment to temporarily

render patients unconscious. This gas acts quickly and provides short-term anesthesia. It is also used in beekeeping to calm bees. When bees start fighting with this gas, they calm down for a few minutes, and then get to know each other again, as if they had lost their memory.

This gas was used in medicine during the COVID-19 epidemic. It was used to improve the effect of oxygen when used together with concentrated oxygen. Nitrous oxide is used in the engines of some sports cars. It increases the high power of the engine and thus allows the car to temporarily increase its speed. This is called the "NOS" (Nitrous Oxide System) and is used to provide high speed.

NO plays an important biochemical role in the body, helping to dilate blood vessels, helping to improve blood flow, because it dilates blood vessels and increases blood permeability. Therefore, NO is useful in high blood pressure or cardiovascular diseases, its vasodilating properties improve the circulatory system. This information is not only interesting for students, but also part of today's modern method, sustainable development education.

RESULTS

Teaching the topic of oxides is of great importance in sustainable development, as oxides are one of the important components of the chemical industry and are widely used in many industrial processes, ecology, energy and other fields. There are several important aspects of learning about oxides in achieving sustainable development:

Energy efficiency and renewables: Oxides play an important role in the collection and storage of solar energy. For example, oxides (SiO_2) are used for solar cells. They help in the efficient generation of energy, thereby contributing to the progress towards sustainable electricity sources.

Environmental protection: Oxides can be used to reduce atmospheric pollution. For example, oxides play an important role in creating catalysts to eliminate polluting gases such as carbon monoxide (CO_2) and nitrogen oxides (NO_x). This is necessary to preserve the environment and prevent climate change.

Protective materials and technologies: Oxides can be used as building materials, for example, as protective coatings against corrosion. For sustainable development, it is important that building and infrastructure materials are durable and environmentally friendly.

Industrial and production efficiency: Oxides, such as metal oxides, play an important role in optimizing production processes. Oxides play a key role in creating new materials and technologies, which helps to save resources and reduce energy consumption.

Thus, teaching the topic of oxides is necessary not only for studying chemistry, but also for mastering the principles of sustainable development. This topic will introduce young people to modern science and technology, helping them build a sustainable society in the future.

DISCUSSION

It would be appropriate to use the “Assessment” method in teaching the topic of sustainable development and oxides in harmony.

Assessment is an English word that means “assessment”, “evaluation”. The history of this method dates back to the 30s-40s of the last century. The English and German military developed this method to select literate and enterprising officers, qualified soldiers who could manage military situations and take adequate action. Later, this method was applied to the world of business. Manufacturing and trading companies began to use this method to identify qualified top managers. Today, it also has its importance in the field of education. Now we are applying this method to the topic of oxides and sustainable development.

<p>Test</p> <p>How many types of oxides are there based on their reactions with water, bases, and acids?</p> <p>A. 3 B. 4 C. 5 A. D. There is no such type at all</p>	<p>Problematic situation</p> <p>Cars were invented to make human life easier, but the acidic oxides they emit cause several environmental problems. Students, think about what these problems are and try to write down their chemical reactions.</p>
<p>Symptoms</p> <p>Explain the following words and write their chemical reactions</p> <p>1. Acid rain 2. Temporary water hardness 1. 3. Global warming</p>	<p>Practical skills</p> <p>1. Obtaining oxides from simple substances</p> <p>1. 2. Show and explain the processes of obtaining oxides from complex substances</p>

CONCLUSION

In teaching the topic of sustainable development and oxides in harmony, the "Assessment" method is an important tool for determining the knowledge and skills acquired by students, as well as for assessing the effectiveness of the teacher in the teaching process.

This method allows you to monitor the changes that occur in the learning process of students, to determine their success in learning. The topics of sustainable development and oxides are often related to scientific, technical and environmental aspects, and the "Assessment" method in assessing these topics shows not only knowledge, but also how students understand, consolidate and apply the topic in practice.

Using the assessment method in teaching education on sustainable development allows you to form environmental awareness in students and teach them to make responsible decisions for sustainable development in society. In the case of oxides, assessment helps to understand and apply chemical processes in practice.

The "Assessment" method is an important tool in the teaching process and is an effective way to determine, consolidate and develop the level of mastery of students. This method allows the teacher to determine in which areas students need help, and also helps to deepen their understanding of complex topics such as sustainable development and oxides.

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